

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

[MOOC]

SPOKE 5 – Industry of Health and Silver Economy

DELIVERABLE DN 9.3

Version history

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the original project plan, a MOOC specifically dedicated to training healthcare professionals in the use of the sarcopenia signature was envisaged. As detailed in Milestone 6, the MOOC was replaced by a scientific symposium with the same aim, entitled “Current Management of Cancer Cachexia and was included among the Lifelong Learning Initiatives (LLI) of WP4.

“Current Management of Cancer Cachexia” was an educational session organized by Prof. Paola Costelli, leader researcher of Spoke 5, and Prof. Fabio Penna within the framework of the 8th International Cancer Cachexia Conference. The session was held on 27 September 2025 at the Aldo Moro Auditorium of the University of Turin and had a duration of 1.5 hours. The course was delivered in English and in person, with the participation of approximately 200 learners, including students, researchers, and representatives from companies.

The session provided participants with the opportunity to deepen their knowledge of the management of cancer cachexia, a highly debilitating syndrome frequently affecting cancer patients and significantly exacerbated by aging. The adopted format was a round-table discussion, in which several experts addressed the management of patients with neoplastic cachexia from their specific professional perspectives. Ample space was dedicated to audience interaction, fostering an interactive learning environment. The session focused on patient-centered interventions, nutritional counseling and support, novel therapeutic approaches, and the preservation of quality of life. In addition, the session included care-giver experience and the helpful role of patient associations. Participants benefited from updated scientific evidence and its practical applications, as well as from the exchange of perspectives with faculty members.

The topic was fully aligned with the “Health Industry & Silver Economy” research and innovation programme (NODES, Spoke 5) and aimed at providing knowledge on innovative and digital strategies for the care of frail individuals, together with sustainable diagnostic and therapeutic tools. Moreover, the session fulfilled one of the objectives of the NODES projects by leveraging research results as inputs for transversal competence-building activities within the Spoke and the broader ecosystem. Finally, the theme was consistent with WP3 of the INNDIANA project, which focuses on the development of tools to address frailty.